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The Spectral Symptoms of Autism: The Scriptural-Nosographical Narrative from the Christian Perspective

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Abstract

In tracing the first recorded case of autism, the author came across a passage on a boy purportedly identified with autism found in three of the four gospels in the New Testament of the Holy Bible. The case probably happened sometime around AD 30-32, when a father with his son afflicted with autistic symptoms brought him to seek healing from Jesus Christ and His disciples. In this paper, the author has taken the passage from the gospel according to Saint Mark (Chapter 9, Verses 17-29) from the New Testament of the Christian holy book to examine the case. The author's goal of this paper is his attempt to find out if there is some form of a treatment for autism available or recorded in the Christian scripture but has not been known, discovered or fully understood. All the scriptural verses cited in this paper are taken from the New International Version (NIV) of the Holy Bible unless stated otherwise.

Keywords: Autism, Autistic Symptoms, Gospel, Jesus (Christ), Saint Mark

Introduction

According to the Centre for Disease Control & Prevention (CDC) Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring (ADDM) Network (CDC, 2012), it has been estimated that for every 59 children in the United States, one is identified or diagnosed with autism. Autism is a condition that has been reported to occur in all races of both genders across ethnicities, nationalities and socio-economic groups throughout the world. It is about four times more common among boys than among girls. In the United States alone, for example, it is estimated that one out of 54 boys and one in 252 girls are diagnosed with autism. Studies elsewhere (e.g., Asia, Europe, and North America) have identified individuals with autism with an average prevalence of between 1% and 2%. South Korea, Japan, Taiwan, Hong Kong and Singapore have reported an increase in the prevalence of autism in their respective populations. In the United States, for example, between the years 2006 and 2008, about one in six school-aged children have a developmental disability ranging from mild disabilities (e.g., speech & language impairments) to serious developmental disabilities (e.g., autism, intellectual and developmental disabilities, and cerebral palsy) (CDC, 2012).

Timeline of Autism

Many professionals and researchers have always wondered when autism first appeared in this world. There are those who have claimed that it is the result of gradual genetic mutation in the human DNA. Others disagreed and argued that the Human Genome Project set up to map out the entire genetic makeup of the humankind has found that "the DNA coding for proteins were only around 3% and the rest of it 97% was actually 'junk' DNA, meaning DNA that did not seemingly code for any protein, and therefore, of no particular 'use' for humans" (Rajalakshmi, 2015, p.1). In other words, Rajalakshmi (2016) considered the project a failure and argued that it has failed to answer the key question: "Why would nature and evolution consider it vital to have the presence of these 'junk' DNA that constitutes the major part of the DNA in human being. Wouldn't it be more scientific to actually explore the importance of this 'junk' DNA instead of dismissing them as 'useless'?" (p.2). Still others have

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postulated that it is the result of our changing lifestyle or it is caused by epigenetic changes (e.g., smoking and air pollution) which interfere with our biological mechanism that will switch our genes on and off. Whatever it is, the findings from studies on autism about its causation remain inconclusive.

In tracing the first recorded case of autism, this author came across a passage on a case of suspected autism found in three of the four gospels in the New Testament of the Holy Bible. It is estimated that the case happened sometime between AD 30 and 32, when a father with a boy with purportedly autistic symptoms brought him to seek healing from Jesus Christ, who spent three years ministering to the Jewish population as well as several Gentiles before His crucifixion in AD 33.

Further down the road between AD 960-1279, ancient Chinese records have been found on treatment for people with autistic conditions during the Song dynasty right to the Qing dynasty. In fact, the highest number of prescriptions for autism treatment peaked during the Ming dynasty (AD 1368-1644) (Cai et al., 2015).

Centuries later, the earliest well-documented case – perhaps the first court case – of autism involving a man by the name Hugh Blair of Borgue’s brother petitioned to annul Blair’s marriage to his wife to get his inheritance took place in 1747. Blair was noted to show very strong autistic symptoms (Houston & Frith, 2000). Another interesting case reported in 1798 is that of the Wild Boy of Aveyron - a feral child who lived in the wild for seven years - brought back into society. Several attempts were made to teach the boy language and social skills but without much success.

In 1911, Dr Eugen Bleuler (b.1857-d.1939), a Swiss psychiatrist, first coined the term *autism* observed in people with dementia and also in schizophrenia. Almost 30 years later, in the United States, Dr Leo Kanner (b.1894-d.1981), an Austrian-American psychiatrist, reported his young patients manifesting symptoms of infantile autism. A year later in 1944, in Germany, Dr Hans Asperger (b.1906-d.1980), an Austrian pediatrician, reported his high-functioning patients who exhibited autistic traits. The latter condition has been named as Asperger’s Syndrome.

The operating definition of autism has been changing over the past decades and it can be traced from the very first edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual (DSM) to its latest fifth edition. However, it is not within the scope of this paper to discuss about it.

From Folklore and Folk Religion to Christian Scriptural Record

The author of this paper has always been intrigued by autism and began his exploration of autism by searching through the mythologies and came to learn about changelings. There are people who believe that a child with autism is a changeling, which is a creature found in folklore and folk religion. According to Wikipedia (2018), “[A] changeling child was believed to be a fairy child that had been left in place of a human child stolen by the fairies. The theme of the swapped child is common in medieval literature and reflects concern over infants thought to be afflicted with unexplained diseases, disorders (*including autism*), or developmental disabilities” (para.1). Later, the author’s curiosity about autism directed him to examine the purportedly first case of autism mentioned in one of the three gospels found in the New Testament of the Holy Bible. He came across an online article written by Chiemelu (2013) about the case.

However, in order to understand autism from so many perspectives with different narratives describing about the condition, it is important to maintain a balanced perspective or narrative. This author has chosen to adopt the Anderson-Jacobson framework (see Figure 1) as this paper focuses on the autistic condition from the Christian perspective. According to Anderson and Jacobson (2003), there is a current worldwide movement shifting toward wholistic health. In fact, today, the prevailing religion in many mainstream communities throughout the world is New Ageism. In the Christian context, “wholistic health requires the integration of our Christian beliefs in many disciplines ... cannot expect ... pastors to have the knowledge of medical doctors, nor can we expect ... medical doctors to have the knowledge of ... pastors. And both will lack the ... skills of a well-trained Christian therapist” (Anderson & Jacobson, 2003, p.67).

According to Anderson and Jacobson (2003), “Christ is the wonderful counsellor, the great physician, and the author and finisher of our faith. He is the only perfectly balanced person to ever live on planet Earth, and we need to learn from Him and be led by Him. He occupies the center of the following diagram” (p.67-68). Readers interested to find out more about this balanced perspective is advised to refer to Anderson and Johnson (2003) (see References).

Fig.1: A Balanced Perspective (Anderson & Jacobson, 2003, p.68)

The four gospels according to Saint Matthew, Saint Mark, Saint Luke and Saint John respectively have provided accounts filled with numerous stories of sicknesses that include various sensory impairments (e.g., deafness, blindness, mutism), physical handicap, leprosy and also dying/death, being miraculously healed by Jesus Christ. All these events recorded in the four gospels took place more than 2000 years ago and people living during that period had different terms used to describe such conditions and also with different explanations. Moreover, with limited understanding about the diseases and disorders that we know, understand and see today, many of those people at that time believed that such problems were caused by evil spirits. To these people, they believed the bad spirits could possess their bodies and hence caused them to act and behave abnormally.

In relation to autism, there is this familiar story of a boy purportedly to manifest autistic traits brought to Christ Jesus by the boy's father desperately in need of help and support not readily available during those days. This story can be found reported in three out of the four gospels. This author has selected to use the same account recorded in the gospel of Saint Mark in writing this paper.

In addition, this author has also chosen to use the Anderson-Jacobson Five-Grid Framework (Anderson & Jacobson, 2003) as shown in Figure 2 for this paper as the

platform upon which the scriptural-nosographical narrative of autism will be discussed. Anderson and Jacobson (2003) have listed five grids (p.28):

■ **The 1st Grid - History**

This grid concerns the understanding of the the history of autism and how it came about, especially its original term, symptoms, causes and changing definitions of the condition over time.

■ **The 2nd Grid - Faith**

This focuses on our understanding of the autism that flows from a foundation of religious beliefs.

■ **The 3rd Grid - Wholistic Knowledge**

This grid asks the following key question: "Does our understanding of autism properly address the whole person (spirit, soul and body) or just one dimension?" (Anderson & Jacobson, 2003, p.28)

■ **The 4th Grid - Science**

This grid asks the following key question: "How does the approach to our understanding of autism in question line up with natural law?" (Anderson & Jacobson, 2003, p.28)

■ **The 5th Grid - Spiritual Discernment**

In this fifth and last grid, Anderson and Jacobson (2003) warned the readers that they have to approach the subject of autism with the Spirit of Truth (see 1 John 4:1; 1 Timothy 4:1 as mentioned in the New Testament of the Holy Bible).

Fig.2: The Anderson-Jacobson Five-Grid Framework

As mentioned earlier, the case study of the boy purportedly afflicted with autism is taken from Mark 9:17-29 (see the full passage below). In the gospel according to Saint Mark chapter 9 verses 17 to 29, it narrates a story of Jesus healing a young boy. This boy has often been described in

literature as having been healed of *epilepsy* because he had a seizure right before Jesus heals him, but *the boy's affliction was more than epilepsy* (see Chiemelu, 2013, for detail). The boy in the story suffered from what doctors today would call *autism*.

¹⁷ A men in the crowd answered, "Teacher, I brought you my son, who is possessed by a spirit that has robbed him of speech. ¹⁸ Whenever it seizes him, it throws him to the ground. He foams at the mouth, gnashes his teeth and becomes rigid. I asked your disciples to drive out the spirit, but they could not."

¹⁹ "You unbelieving generation," Jesus replied, "how long shall I stay with you? How long shall I put up with you? Bring the boy to me."

²⁰ So they brought him. When the spirit saw Jesus, it immediately threw the boy into a convulsion. He fell to the ground and rolled around, foaming at the mouth.

²¹ Jesus asked the boy’s father, “How long has he been like this?”
 “From childhood,” he answered. ²² “It has often thrown him into fire or water to kill him. But if you can do anything, take pity on us and help us.”
²³ “If you can?” said Jesus. “*Everything is possible for one who believes.*”
²⁴ Immediately the boy’s father exclaimed, “I do believe; help me overcome my unbelief!”
²⁵ When Jesus saw that a crowd was running to the scene, he rebuked the impure spirit. “You deaf and mute spirit,” he said, “I command you, come out of him and never enter him again.”
²⁶ The spirit shrieked, convulsed him violently and came out. The boy looked so much like a corpse that many said, “He’s dead.” ²⁷ But *Jesus took him by the hand and lifted him to his feet, and he stood up.*
²⁸ After Jesus had gone indoors, his disciples asked him privately, “Why couldn’t we drive it out?”
²⁹ He replied, “*This kind can come out only by prayer (and fasting).*”

From the verses in the passage recorded in Chapter 9 of the gospel of Saint Mark, the following symptoms (underlined) have been identified in Mark 9:17-26 (see Table 1 below):

Table 1: Autistic Symptoms as identified in Mark 9:17-26

Verses	Phrases that depict the autistic symptoms
17	... Who is possessed by a spirit that has <u>robbed him of speech?</u>
18	... Whenever it seizes him, it <u>throws him to the ground. He foams at the mouth, gnashes his teeth and becomes rigid.</u>
19	... It immediately threw the boy into <u>a convulsion. He fell to the ground and rolled around, foaming at the mouth.</u>
21	<u>From childhood</u>
22	It has <u>often thrown him into fire or water to kill him.</u>
25	... <u>deaf and mute</u> spirit
26	The spirit shrieked, <u>convulsed him violently and came out.</u> The boy <u>looked so much like a corpse ... He’s dead.</u>

The Five Broad Spectral Symptoms of Autism and Other Autistic Traits

To understand what these spectral symptoms that constitute autism, we need to know what exactly autism is though even until today, there is no one fully agreed definition of the condition. Generally, autism is seen as a group of developmental brain disorders, collectively called autism spectrum disorder (ASD). The term "spectrum" (singular) or “spectra” (plural) refers to the wide range of symptoms, skills, and levels of impairment, or disability, that child with autism exhibit. Some children are mildly impaired by

their autistic traits or symptoms, but others can be severely disabled with intellectual and developmental challenges and are non-verbal. There are five broad spectra of symptoms – social interaction, communication, stereotypical behavior, sensory response/reaction, and task behavior – that are often observed in individuals (both children and adults) with autism, ranging from one end that displays signs of low passivity to the other end that shows signs of high activity or reactivity to either external or internal stimuli (or even to both external and internal stimuli simultaneously) shown in Figure 3 below.

Fig.3: Five Broad Spectral Symptoms of Autism (Xie, 2018)

These five spectral symptoms of autism can be rated on the 5-point Likert scale with (1 = low passivity, 3 = normativity, and 5 = high activity/reativity to help in us in

better understanding the varying degree of functional severity in autism (see Table 2 below).

Table 2: Rating and Understanding of Spectral Symptoms of Autism

Spectral Symptoms	1	2	3	4	5
Social Interaction	Sedentary	Socially inept	Socially appropriate	Eloping	Hyperactive
Communication	Nonverbal	Vocalising	Verbal	Echolalic	Hyperlexic
Stereotypical Behaviour	Self-stimulatory	Ritualistic behaviour	Self-aware	Pica behaviour	Self-injurious
Sensory Response	Sensory avoidance	Sensory hyper-responsive	Sensory modulation	Sensory hypo-responsive	Sensory seeking
Task Behaviour	La belle indifference	Sporadic reactive	Compliant responsive	Resistance	Demand avoidance

For example, a child with autism may display sensory avoidance from some external sensory stimulus (e.g., noise) that he strongly dislikes and so starts humming to himself. Another child with autism may be hypo-sensitive/hypo-responsive to noise and so is always craving for more of it to the extent that he is always seeking auditory stimulation (sensory seeking habit). The opposite of it is hyper-sensitivity/hyper-responsivity. However, there is more to just the horizontal continuum of each of the five broad spectral symptoms. There is also the

vertical continuum for each of the broad spectral symptoms. For example, children with autism may not have spontaneous speech production and they manifest severe handicaps in communication (see Figure 4 below): non-verbalization (poor social relating), babbling (non-meaningful vocalizations), low intelligibility (expressive delay and deviance), and stereotypy (repetitiveness) (Krug, Arick, & Almond, 1993). It is not within the scope of this paper to explore this issue.

Fig.4: An Example of Vertical Continuum of the Spectral Symptom of Communication

Returning to the passage taken from Mark 9, the Table 3 below shows a comparison of purportedly autistic symptoms/traits identified in Mark 9:17-26 with those typical symptoms of autism that are known today: (a) On

the left column is a list of symptoms identified as autistic traits in verses from Mark 9, and (b) on the right column is the list of the typical autistic symptoms or traits that we know today.

Table 3: A Comparison of Mark 9:17-26 and Typical Autistic Symptoms

Verses from Mark 9:17-26 that tell of autistic symptoms/traits	Autistic symptoms or traits that are known today
v.17: robbed him of speech v.18: seizes ... throws him down ... foams at the mouth ... gnashes his teeth ... becomes rigid v.20: a convulsion. He fell to the ground and rolled around, foaming at the mouth v.21: from childhood v.22: It has often thrown him into fire or water to kill him v.25: deaf and mute spirit v.26: ... shrieked, convulsed him violently and came out v.26 ... looked so much like a corpse ... He's dead.	v.17: Non-verbal v.18: Febrile convulsion or epileptic fit (epilepsy) v.20: Epileptic fit or convulsion v.21: Onset of the condition takes place during early childhood phase v.22: Self-injurious behaviour v.25: Unresponsive to people when call and is also known as nonverbal v.26: Severe epileptic fit; unresponsive after the episode like dead v.26: Syncope (fainting spell)

Among the spectral symptoms of autism identified in the verses taken from the gospel according to Saint Mark chapter 9, each of the autistic symptoms will be elaborated further below.

Symptom #1: Convulsion

According to Oxford Dictionaries online (see <https://www.oxforddictionaries.com>), convulsion refers “to the condition in which a sudden, violent, irregular movement of the body, caused by involuntary contraction of muscles and associated especially with brain disorders such as epilepsy, the presence of certain toxins or other agents in the blood, or fever in children” (para.1). For example, symptoms of a febrile convulsion that occurs in young children with autism usually include the following:

- body stiffness (like a *corpse* as mentioned in Mark 9);
- jerky movements (*fall and roll around*);
- loss of consciousness or syncope (blacking out);
- eyes rolling back in the head (as if *being possessed by a spirit*);
- shallow breathing or altered breathing; and
- deep sleep for an hour or so afterwards (*as if dead*, also mentioned in Mark 9).

As recorded in the gospel according to Saint Mark 9:18, the desperate father explained to Jesus that his son or the boy had seizures. Having limited knowledge and without a full understanding the condition, the boy’s father could only attribute the cause of the seizures to a mute spirit. Today it is estimated that as many as one third of individuals with autism also have epilepsy (see Furfaro, 2018, for details).

Symptom #2: Early Onset of Autism

As reported in gospel of Mark 9:20-22, when Jesus asked the stricken boy’s father how long the boy had been like

that (see Mark 9:21), he replied that it was from childhood (Mark 9:22). The boy’s father attributed all the early onset of these spectral symptoms of autism to a mute spirit said to have been afflicting his son or the boy since childhood. Since the boy is still a child, childhood in his case is still within the phase of early childhood, which is the period when autism occurs and is evident in young children. Generally, the onset of autism is observed to be between 2-3 to about 5 years of age. This is early-onset autism. Currently, there is no official diagnosis called late-onset autism. In fact, the DSM-5 (American Psychiatrists Association, 2013), which lists and describes all developmental and mental disorders, has clearly stated that the onset of the autistic symptoms is in the early developmental period.

Symptom #3: Challenging Behaviors in Autism

Parents and teachers who have dealing with children with autism know how difficult and challenging in coping with their behaviors. In terms of challenging behaviors, there are three different levels:

- Sensory perceptual-motor processing and coordination behavior (i.e., sensory responsivity, sensory processing, and sensory regulation)
- Adaptive behavior (e.g., social interaction, toilet training, and daily living skills)
- Internalizing and externalizing behaviors (e.g., internal self-stimulatory, observable self-injuring, eloping, performing given tasks, etc.)

Chia and Chua (2014) have proposed the four-level hierarchy of sensory perceptual-motor processing and coordination behavior (collectively, it is known as sensation) (see Figure 5 below).

Fig.5: The 4-Level Hierarchy of Sensation (Chia & Chua, 2014)

Briefly described, the first level of sensation concerns the exteroceptive senses, i.e., sight, hearing, touch, smell and taste. This involves the five sensory organs: eyes, ears, tongue, nose and skin. The next level involves interoceptive senses which include vestibule and proprioception. The third level of sensation refers to the mindsight or mindful awareness of the environment around an individual or organism. The fourth level refers to the relational sense in

which an individual interacts with others. This is also known as the sense of being and belongingness. No man is an island, as a saying goes, and everyone needs others in order to keep one’s sanity since human is a social and NOT sedentary being. However, an individual can choose to be anti-social or even asocial and often such a person has some form of personality disorder which includes emotional disturbance.

Moe recently, according to Kipnis (2018), there is another higher level of sensation. This is the immune system. It possesses “the ability to sense them (micro-organisms) and defend against them when needed - is central to survival. Our immune system excels at exactly that, with innate immunity’s ability to generally recognize patterns and types of invaders and adaptive immunity’s talent for recognizing specific invaders” (p.27) the role of the immune system is to detect micro-organisms (or any other pathogens) and inform the brain about them. It is very likely our immune response is hardwired into the brain that would make it another sensory organ or sense.

Symptom #4: Mindless Awareness in Autism

The term mindless awareness is ironical. How is it possible for someone to be aware and yet mindless? Mindlessness is the lack of attention or when the level of alertness is completely absent. One can be aware of what is going on and yet can miss the main point or object because of the lack of focused attention. This is what mindless awareness is and often children with autism display such behavior. In other words, such children do not seem to be aware of what is happening around them, but when asked, they can still answer you. This is actually the same kind of experience referring to the type of spirit that was afflicting the boy mentioned in Mark 9:17-29. Almost over 2000 years ago, these children like the boy described in the gospel of Mark chapter 9, threw themselves into fire or water to destroy themselves. They are described as exhibiting mindless awareness or mind-blindness without the fear of danger. In 2012, the National Autism Association conducted a survey and found that from 2009 to 2011, accidental drowning accounted for 91% total U.S. deaths reported of mind-blindness in children with autism subsequent to their wandering or eloping.

Symptom #5: Self-Injurious Behavior in Autism

As mentioned in Mark 9:22, because the afflicted boy’s father understood that a spirit had caused his son’s *violent* behavior, he describes “the spirit” as “throwing” his son into fire and water on different occasions to “try to kill him.” This behavior is found in the 3rd spectrum of autistic symptoms (see Figure 3 and Table 2) and has been

described as challenging sensory issues. It can be in low passivity as in *self-stimulatory behavior* or in high activity/reactivity seen in *self-injurious behavior*. If an individual can regulate his stereotypical behavior, he/she is described as in normativity. In most instances of individuals with autism, normativity is partially present but often absent.

Symptom #6: Elopement - Mindless Externalizing Behavior in Autism

Today children with autism are known to manifest mindless externalizing behaviour (or what is termed as “elopement”) that includes “wandering, bolting, or eloping” to unsafe areas like water and traffic. As a result of their mind-blindness, children with autism exhibit poor social relational sense. This is also another mindless externalizing behaviour observed. About 50% of children with autism wander from safe to unsafe environments and about one third of these eloping children with autism are non-verbal, just like the boy described in the gospel of Saint Mark 9.

Elopement is one of the several common autistic mindless externalizing behavioural traits. It is also known as wandering or bolting. It refers to an individual’s externalizing behaviour of leaving an area without permission or supervision. The individual does it without even being mindfully aware. It is also termed as *mindless* mind-blindness more severe than another person with *mindful* mind-blindness. There is a difference between the former (known as obliviousness) and the latter, which refers to narrow attention targeted on one thing to the extent of excluding others around. Figure 6 shows where obliviousness (mindless mindblindness and narrow attention (mindful mindblindness) are located in the mind-based model of Theory of Mind (ToM) in autism. Because such mindless or mind-blind habit, elopement can put an individual with autism, related intellectual and/or developmental disabilities at risk for harm/danger to himself/herself. Hence, both parents of such children and teachers working with these children must always be on the lookout for them just in case they elope to somewhere else without anyone’s knowing.

Fig.6: Mind-based Model of the Theory of Mind (Chia & Chua, 2014)

Some possible reasons why individuals with autism may elope are that they want to avoid something, to obtain access to an item, activity, or person, or to engage in an intrinsically pleasurable activity such as running or spinning. Often, therapists carry out what is known as functional behaviour analysis/assessment, i.e., a behaviour analysis method of investigating the causes of behaviour, to

provide them a useful measure to record/report on the frequency of elopement and also what may have triggered elopement, but each episode of elopement varies from person to person. Currently, there is no research or evidence to support the hypothesis that individuals elope as a result of physiological arousal or access to repetitive behaviour.

Symptom #7: Poor Task Behavior in Autism

A good example of poor task behavior observed in children with autism is the pathological demand avoidance (PDA) or extreme demand avoidance (EDA) behavior. It is also known as task avoidance behavior. The central difficulty for individuals with PDA/EDA is their avoidance of the everyday demands made by other people, due to their high anxiety levels when they feel that they are not in control. Hence, the name of the syndrome: pathological demand avoidance. Individuals with PDA/EDA will avoid demands made by others, due to their high anxiety levels when they feel that they are not in control. If pressured further, they can turn aggressive; develop a terrible meltdown or syncope (fainting spell) just to avoid something they do not want to be involved. Especially syncope, “[S]ometimes when people suffer faint, their muscles twitch and their bodies make jerking movements; this can sometimes be confused with seizures but are not actual seizures” (CDC, 2015, para. 1). As in the case of the boy described in Mark 9:26, “*The spirit shrieked, convulsed him violently and came out. The boy looked so much like a corpse that many said, ‘He’s dead.’*” The boy broke into an epileptic fit and followed by a syncope stressed by the episode when he was brought by his father to meet Jesus. Today, PDA/EDA is increasingly recognized as part of the autism spectrum.

Symptom #8: Deaf and Mutism in Autism

As recorded in Mark 9:17, the father described his son being afflicted with “a mute spirit.” It means that his son was unable to talk. About 25% of individuals with autism are non-verbal. This is exactly what has been referred to “having a mute spirit” in Jesus’ time. In Mark 9:18, the father also explained that the boy had seizures, and today it is estimated that as many as one third of individuals with autism also have epilepsy. The boy’s father attributed the cause of the seizures to the mute spirit. This is how people in the past without full understanding of the causes of autism understood about the challenging condition. Jesus also referred to this spirit as a *deaf and mute/dumb*

spirit (Mark9:25). The boy did not respond when spoken to and so he might be taken as deaf. This accounts for the spirit being characterized as deaf since many children with autism also do not respond to their names or when people speak to them. Jesus also characterizes the spirit as being a dumb spirit. The reason is obvious: children with autism do not respond or speak.

The question is often asked is: What does the term “spirit” mean? According to the Cambridge English Dictionary (2018) (see <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/spirit>), it defines spirit as follows: “the characteristics of a person that are considered as being separate from the body, and that many religions believe continue to exist after the body dies” (para.20). The term “spirit” also refers to “a state of mind or attitude” (Cambridge English Dictionary, 2018, para.38). There are also other definitions for the term ‘spirit’. In this paper, the author has chosen the latter to refer to the abnormal state of mind or attitude that has afflicted an individual with autism.

This author has also attempted to differentiate between the spirit and the soul, which are often confused by many people including the Christians themselves. According to the Bibles for America (2018), the term *spirit* refers to that innermost part of one’s being that receives God and contacts Him. When he/she receives Jesus as his/her personal Saviour, this is where He came to live in his/her heart. In this spirit or the new heart, the person can now have fellowship with the Lord and spend time in His presence.

According to Smith (2013), the Holy Bible reveals that man is made up of the three parts, i.e., spirit, soul and body as mentioned in First Thessalonians 5:23, where Saint Paul the Apostle mentioned: “May God himself, the God of peace, sanctify you through and through. May your whole spirit, soul and body be kept blameless at the coming of our Lord Jesus Christ.” Figure 7 below illustrates the three parts of man.

Fig.7: The Three Parts of Man (Smith, 2013)

Smith (2013) has clearly described the three parts of man and how they are differentiated one from the others. The outermost circle refers to the *body*, which is the man’s outer part containing his five senses use in contact with all the things in the physical, material realm (see Smith, 2013, para.12). The middle circle refers to the *soul*, which is the man’s inner part containing his mind (cognition), emotion

(affect) and will (conation) with which he contacts all the things in the psychological realm (see Smith, 2013, para.13). The innermost circle refers to the man’s *spirit*, which is his innermost part with which he contacts God and substantiates all the things in the spiritual realm (see Smith, 2013, para.14).

Figure 8 elaborates on the spirit (inner circle) and the soul (middle circle) according to interpretation of Anderson and Jacobson (2003). The spirit represents the new heart. The soul is divided into three parts: mind (cognition), emotions (affect) and will (conation). The tangible organ of mind is the brain whose key role is to think. It is regulated by the

central nervous system. The emotions and the will are regulated by the peripheral nervous system. The autonomic nervous system governs the emotions (i.e., to feel) while the somatic nervous system controls the will (i.e., to choose).

Fig.8: Spirit and Soul of a Man (Anderson & Jacobson, 2003)

In autism, cognitive, affective and conative behavioral potentials (see Poland, 1974, for detailed explanation) of an individual are impaired. Mentalizing, which is a high-level component of social cognition that enables a person to infer the mental states of other minds (e.g., beliefs and thoughts) (Brüne, 2005; Penn et al., 2008), is the process that underlies cognition (mind, i.e., to think). Systemizing, which refers to the ability to analyze and build system so as to understand and predict the functional behavior of impersonal events or inanimate or abstract entities (Baron-Cohen et al., 2003), is the process that underlies conation (will, i.e., to choose). Empathizing, which refers to the ability to make connection to another person’s experience and to respond appropriately to that person, is the process that underlies affect (emotions, i.e., to feel). Individuals with autism are often impaired in mentalizing and empathizing but may display a superior systemizing ability. In other words, the *soul* is displaying issues of concern and in turn inflicts the *body* with challenging problems. The *spirit*, which is the channel that allows the person to know God and be in contact with Him, is left untouched. This may help to explain why miracles can still happen the moment an individual’s spirit gets in contact with the Lord in prayer (and fasting) and to meditate on God’s Word. This is spiritual discipline. Rather than seeking an emotional feeling when praying or thinking about the Bible and trying to understand God’s Word in an intellectual or mental way through reading the scripture, an individual must learn to turn deeply to the Lord and be right in his/her spirit (see Bibles for America, 2018, for more detail).

Causation of Autism

According to the Autism Society (2015), “[T]here is no known single cause for autism spectrum disorder, but it is generally accepted that it is caused by abnormalities in brain structure or function. Brain scans show differences in the shape and structure of the brain in children with autism compared to in neurotypical children” (para. 1). In other

words, the causation of autism and its many autistic behavioural traits is still inconclusive. Today, autism experts, professional practitioners and researchers are not certain about the exact cause of autism but are still investigating a number of theories, including the links among heredity, genetics and medical problems. As a result, many different theories as well as new hypotheses are continuously being proposed to explain the causes of autism over the past several years. None of them has explained satisfactorily the causation of autism.

The autistic condition could be caused by a foreign entity such as epigenetic factors (e.g., smoking and water pollution), exogenic factors (e.g., pathogens) and endogenic factors (e.g., peripheral immune cells attacking microglial cells in the brain resulting in some kind of an autoimmune disorder) and the same can be said of the purportedly autistic boy described in Mark 9.

What is the Best Approach to help Individuals with Autism

In the case of the father with his son described in Mark 9:23-24, Jesus told the boy’s father that “Everything is possible for one who believes.” Immediately the boy’s father exclaimed, “I do believe; help me overcome my unbelief!”

In the subsequent part of Mark 9:27-29, the gospel described how Jesus took the boy by the hand and lifted him to his feet, and he stood up. In verse 28, after Jesus had gone indoors, his disciples asked him privately, “Why couldn’t we drive it out?” Finally, Jesus explained to them, “This kind can come out only by prayer (and fasting)” (Mark 9:29).

There are three key points to learn from this passage taken from Mark 9:23-24 and they are as follows:

- Verse 23: “Everything is possible for one who believes.”
- Verse 27: Jesus took him by the hand and lifted him to his feet, and he stood up.

- Verse 29: “This kind can come out only by prayer (and fasting).”

Each of these points will be discussed briefly below.

Point #1: Mark 9:23 - “Everything is possible for one who believes.”

What does it mean that “[E]verything is possible for one who believes”? To believe and if a person chooses to believe, it means the person has to put his/her total faith and trust in God through His Son, Jesus Christ, and that is also to love Him (or God) “with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your mind and with all your

strength” (Mark 12:30). That is often regarded as the first and greatest commandment. The second commandment is found in Mark 12:31: “Love your neighbor as yourself. There is no commandment greater than these.”

The question is: “Who is this neighbor?” He/She can be anyone around us including someone with autism in this case here. A person who is unable to love God will not be able to love his neighbors.

Briefly, this author interprets the verse in the context of supporting a child with autism as follows:

To love ...	What it means biblically ...	What it means to support a child with autism
■ ... with all your heart	To love God with all <i>your heart</i> has to do with AFFECTION.	This means to love a child with autism with compassion and to support him/her with passion.
■ ... with all your soul	To love the Lord by living a life of faithfulness to all that the Lord has required of you and it has to do with DEVOTION.	This means to remain steadfast in supporting the child with autism despite the challenges.
■ ... with all your mind	To dedicate one’s ATTENTION or intellectual awareness to knowing God and think clearly and truly about Him so that one does not have false ideas in the mind.	This means being mindful of the child with autism when supporting him/her and one has to be person-centered in catering to his/her needs.
■ ... with all your strength	To love God with all <i>your strength</i> is to love with your resources, your abilities and your time. It requires one’s full COMMITMENT to act.	This means to assure the child with autism that he/she will always be supported with whatever available resources, time and quality care needed by him/her.

Point #2: Mark 9:27 - Jesus took him by the hand and lifted him to his feet, and he stood up.

In the gospel according to Saint Mark, touch has been mentioned in many verses in different situations. Notice that from these several verses, Jesus simply stretched His hand to touch, to heal and to lay with His hands on many with sicknesses and other afflictions. They were all cured. Below are some of the examples with verses cited from the New American Standard (NAS) version of the Holy Bible:

- Mark 1:41 - Moved with compassion, Jesus *stretched out His hand and touched him*, and said to him, "I am willing; be cleansed."
- Mark 3:10 - for He had *healed many*, with the result that all those who had afflictions pressed around Him in order to *touch Him*.
- Mark 5:27 - after hearing about Jesus, she came up in the crowd behind Him and *touched His cloak*.
- Mark 5:28 - For she thought, "*If I just touch His garments, I will get well.*"
- Mark 6:56 - Wherever He entered villages, or cities, or countryside, they were laying the sick in the market places, and imploring Him that they *might just touch the fringe of His cloak; and as many as touched it were being cured*.
- Mark 7:33 - Jesus took him aside from the crowd, by himself, and put His fingers into his ears, and after spitting, *He touched his tongue with the saliva;*
- Mark 10:16 - And He took them in His arms and began blessing them, *laying His hands on them*.

To take or hold by the hand or lay with hands on someone involves touch. Linden (2015) has argued that touch is the science of hand (conation: to choose), heart (affect: to feel) and mind (cognition: to think) that all come into play. It is an important approach to healing. Several studies (e.g., Bailey, 2012; Feldman, Rosenthal, & Eidelman, 2014; Lawn et al., 2010) have confirmed that skin-to-skin contact

(e.g., kangaroo care for preterm babies in neonatal care) can “improve sleep patterns, cognitive control and mother-child reciprocity” (Linden, 2015, p.29). There are also many types of touch and below are just some four examples given by Linden (2015):

- **Social touch** promotes trust and cooperation as it is associated with warmth, gentleness and safety.
- **Emotional touch** provides a broad range of experiential intentions including support, compliance, appreciation, dominance, attention getting, sexual interest, play and inclusion.
- **Haptic touch** activates tactile stimulation, copes with stress or anxiety, and elicits responses.
- **Physiological touch** informs of pain threshold level, warns of dangerous objects to be avoided, retracts to safety (flee) and/or confronts danger/harm head-on (fight).

Point #3: Mark 9:29 - “This kind can come out only by prayer (and fasting).”

When someone prays, he or she has also to meditate on God’s Word. In some manuscripts, fasting is also included at the end of the verse in Mark 9:29. Prayer and fasting involve some form of spiritual discipline. It concerns the Christian understanding of the divine psychiatry of God (Allen, 1953) in terms of the following four key passages that have provided the Christian sense of coherence in life especially more so for parents who have to manage and cope with their children with autism and teachers who are dedicated to care for such children:

- **Psalm 23:** The Psalm that calms the Soul - How to think of God

The blessings and the calmness of soul expressed in Psalm 23 written by the biblical King David gives delight and solace to parents and teachers are always struggling to cope with challenging behaviors of their children with autism.

Psalm 23 gives them a sense of coherence in their life: comprehensibility (i.e., making sense of what is happening around oneself), manageability (i.e., using available resources to cope with one's daily challenges in life) and

meaningfulness (i.e., coming to terms with a meaningful purpose for one's life) (see Antonovsky, 1979, 1987, for more detail).

Fig.9: Model of the Sense of Coherence (Antonovsky, 1979, 1987)

■ **Exodus 20:1-17:** The Ten Commandments - God's rules for living

The first four commandments of the ten focus on the believers' relationship with God. The remaining six commandments concern their relationship with fellow human beings. Jesus has summarised the 10 commandments into two as follows:

1. "Love the Lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your mind and with all your strength" (Mark 12:30); and
2. "The second is this: 'Love your neighbour as yourself'" (Mark 12:31).

As mentioned earlier in Point #1, by loving God, they should also show love to their neighbors including those with autism!

■ **Matthew 6:9-13:** The Lord's Prayer - How to talk to God

Jesus has provided His disciples as well as the Christians today a perfect example of how to pray to God. Today this prayer is known as The Lord's Prayer. Many Christians can recite it from memory, but Jesus did say that prayer is not repeating the same words over and over. Jesus wanted to tell His disciples the type of prayer to pray. These things are the type of things that God will honour the prayers:

1. Giving praise & glory to God;
2. Expressing their needs;
3. Seeking His forgiveness; and finally,
4. Seeking His grace to deliver them from worldly desires & temptations.

When applied in the context of parents and teachers struggling to manage the challenging behavior of their children with autism, it means to put their full faith and trust in God by praising Him for who He is and what He can do. This is adopting a positive attitude and also in recognizing one's limitations. It can help to reduce self-blame which, in turn, can become self-defeating and cause a parent or teacher to become discouraged. Next, it concerns expressing the needs of parents and teachers in giving them the resilience and strength to cope with their struggles in managing these children with autism. This is followed by confession of their shortcomings in what they are doing for these children as well as in seeking forgiveness. This is an important step that every parent and teacher should take note. Nobody is perfect and everyone can make mistakes out of frustration or at the loss of what to do. As one saying goes, "we should just need to do our

best and to God we leave the rest." Finally, parents and teachers are always tempted to give up when they see no successful results despite what they have done so much for children with autism. This last part of the prayer is a call to God for strength to stay resilient and deliverance from failure and discouragement in order to persevere.

■ **Matthew 5:2-12:** The Eight Beatitudes - The keys to God's Kingdom

The eight Beatitudes are the supreme blessings preached by Jesus in His Sermon on the Mount to his disciples. Each blessing offers a future reward to the person possessing a specific character quality placed within the context of parents and/or teachers managing their children with autism below:

1. "Blessed are the poor in spirit" (Matthew 5:3):
Feeling poor in spirit or downtrodden in life, especially for parents whose children with autism have grown up and they are often at a loss of what to do with them.
Spiritual reward: "for theirs is the kingdom of heaven" (Matthew 5:3).
2. "Blessed are those who mourn" (Matthew 5:4):
Feeling remorseful, when parents feel that they could have done more when in fact they have given their best to provide for the needs of their child with autism
Spiritual reward: "for they will be comforted" (Matthew 5:4).
3. "Blessed are the meek" (Matthew 5:5):
Staying meek and be submissive is an acknowledgement of one's limitations and the need for parents and/or teachers to open up to share their experience and learn from others.
Spiritual reward: "for they will inherit the earth" (Matthew 5:5).
4. "Blessed are those who hunger and thirst for righteousness" (Matthew 5:6):
Seeking to do right things is exactly what parents and teachers should continue doing so that they can provide the best for their children with autism.
Spiritual reward: "for they will be filled" (Matthew 5:6).
5. "Blessed are the merciful" (Matthew 5:7):
Being merciful and forgiving, especially when someone who does not understand what autism is and says all kinds of wrong or hurtful things (e.g., the child is mentally unsound).
Spiritual reward: "for they will be shown mercy" (Matthew 5:7).

6. *“Blessed are the poor in heart”* (Matthew 5:8):
Being obedient to God, and that is to put one’s faith and trust in Him and that there is a reason for everything that has happened (see the earlier Point #1).
Spiritual reward: *“for they will see God”* (Matthew 5:8).
7. *“Blessed are the peacemakers”* (Matthew 5:9):
Preserving the peace among all fellow human beings by promoting inclusive living so that both autistic and non-autistic can co-exist in the community
Spiritual reward: *“for they will be called children of God”* (Matthew 5:9).
8. *“Blessed are those who are persecuted because of*

righteousness” (Matthew 5:10):

Enduring persecution (physical, emotional & mental) by parents and their children with autism because they are often ostracized by other adults or their peers respectively. These other people or peers do not understand what autism is or they may have a misperception of the condition.
Spiritual reward: *“for theirs is the kingdom of heaven”* (Matthew 5:10).

Below is Figure 10 that provides a summary of the four scriptural messages taken from the Holy Bible:

Fig.10: A Summary of the Four Key Messages of God’s Psychiatry (Allen, 1953)

Concluding Remark

The story of Jesus reaching out to the father of the purportedly autistic boy is perhaps the earliest recorded case of autism. From the scriptural-nosographical description of the boy’s condition according to the gospel of Saint Mark, the symptoms point to autism as the most likely disorder that afflicted the boy.

Knowing the condition that afflicted the boy is one step closer to finding a solution to treat it. When Jesus was asked by his disciples why they could not drive out the deaf and mute spirit from the purportedly autistic boy, He told them plainly, "This kind can come out only by prayer (and fasting)" (Mark 9:29). There lies the solution that we have been searching for. The pre-requisite is *belief* and that is exactly what Jesus told the boy’s father, “Everything is possible for one who believes” (Mark 9:23). In fact, Jesus once said before, “With man this is impossible, but with God all things are possible.” (Matthew 19:26).

To believe that with God all things are possible, a believer will follow wherever God (or Jesus Christ) leads, obey whatever He asks, and put one’s faith and trust in Him whatever the trial. In this way, the believer is also expressing his/her love for God through His Son, Jesus Christ. Hence, according to Got Questions Ministries (2018), “To love Jesus (or God) is to reflect the love that

God has for us, for ‘[T]his is love: not that we loved God, but that he loved us and sent his Son as an atoning sacrifice for our sins’ (1 John 4:10). To love the Lord is to care for the ones He loves (see 1 John 4:19; John 21:16)” (para. 3). Jesus Himself mentioned two most important commandments relating to love: the first commandment (Mark 12:30) is “to love God with all your heart” (i.e., with affection including compassion and passion), “with all your soul” (i.e., with devotion and full dedication), “with all your mind” (i.e., with attention, not just intellectual awareness) “and with all your strength” (i.e., with commitment including conviction by the Holy Spirit); and the second commandment is “to love your neighbour as yourself” (Mark 12:31). Who is this neighbour? He/She can be anyone including someone with disabilities such as a child with autism as well as his parents. If the parents and teachers can follow the first commandment, surely they will do the same for children or students with autism with the same affection (compassion & passion), support them with devotion (dedication), give them the full attention (mindful awareness) they need and serve them with commitment (conviction). This is where the solution in managing children with autism regardless of the degree of severity. The father of the purportedly autistic son cried to Jesus, "I do believe; help me overcome my unbelief!" This

is exactly what many parents as well as teachers are struggling with their unbelief, thinking that there is nothing more they can do to help their children or students with autism. In fact, the *real* solution lies in them if only they *believe!*

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